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Investigation of the use of Gaseous Fuels as Secondary Fuels in Dual-Fuel Compression Ignition Engines

Çift Yakıtlı Sıkıştırma ile Ateşlemeli Motorlarda İkinci Yakıt Olarak Gaz Yakıtların Kullanılmasının Araştırılması

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Today, sustainability requirements and the goal of increasing engine efficiency have led to a significant rise in scientific interest in dual-fuel compression ignition engine technologies. The effects of using different gaseous fuels such as natural gas, biogas, hydrogen, and syngas as secondary fuels on the combustion characteristics, performance behavior, and emission outputs of dual-fuel compression ignition engines are of great importance. The ability of gaseous fuels to form homogeneous and lean mixtures provides significant reductions in soot and NO_x emissions; moreover, when operating with biomass-derived gases, notable decreases in CO₂ emissions are also achieved. Evaluations indicate that thermal efficiency increases under medium and high load conditions, while the formation of unburned hydrocarbons and CO rises at low loads. Parameters such as ignition delay, air–fuel mixture ratio, pilot diesel quantity, and injection timing have been identified as factors that directly affect the performance of dual-fuel systems. Overall, the findings reveal that gas-fuel-assisted dual-fuel CI engines can offer significant advantages in terms of both efficiency and emissions when properly calibrated.

Keywords: Thermal Efficiency, Emission Analysis, Dual-Fuel Engine, Compression Ignition, Gaseous Fuels

1. INTRODUCTION

With the continuous increase in energy demand, the worsening of air pollution, and concerns that petroleum-based fuels will be insufficient in the long term, researchers have been directed to investigate renewable alternative fuels with cleaner combustion properties that can be used in internal combustion engines. In this context, studies on the usability of various alternative fuels such as biodiesel, methanol, ethanol, biogas, natural gas, LPG, and hydrogen in engine technologies have increased significantly. Research shows that fuels derived from vegetable oils and methyl esters can be used directly instead of diesel without requiring extensive changes in engine design; other types of alternative fuels can be effectively applied in internal combustion engines by incorporating them into the system as a second fuel in most cases

(Ahmed, Zhou et al. 2018). Studies on the use of fuels such as hydrogen, biogas, and synthesis gas in dual-fuel mode with diesel/biodiesel pilot fuel also show that, despite limited performance drops, significant improvements in emissions have been achieved. The literature reveals that various methods have been applied to evaluate the performance of these engines and reduce emissions (Rossha, Dhir et al. 2018). The environmental impacts and depletion risk of fossil fuels have made the use of renewable gaseous fuels such as biogas and biosyngas in diesel engines an important alternative. Using these gases in dual-fuel mode with diesel reduces emissions, but combustion instability and performance loss may occur under certain operating conditions. Recent research shows that advanced combustion strategies and engine adjustments reduce these problems and increase the potential of biomass gases in engine applications (Ai and Cho 2025).

Although there are many studies on combustion and performance in dual-fuel engines running on natural gas and biogas, it is observed that emissions, especially particulate matter, have not been sufficiently investigated. The findings show that PM emissions are reduced by approximately 70% in dual-fuel mode compared to diesel mode, and that smaller, round particle structures are formed. (Mustafi and Raine 2008). The use of compressed natural gas (CNG) in diesel engines is evaluated in terms of exergy and exergoeconomic aspects through experimental tests conducted at different loads. The findings show that CNG use reduces exergy efficiency at low and medium loads and increases exergy losses and costs; however, at full load, the CNG20 mixture in particular yields more advantageous results. Based on total cost flow rates, CNG20 at 75% load and all CNG ratios at full load appear more economical compared to diesel fuel. (Kaya, Aydin et al. 2023). Although diesel-natural gas dual-fuel engines are of interest because they offer lower carbon emissions, increased methane emissions, especially at low loads, pose a significant environmental problem. Although there are comprehensive studies in the literature on performance, combustion, and emission behavior, the effects of parameters such as injection timing, natural gas ratio, and injector tip temperature are still not fully understood. (Dev, Guo et al. 2020).

Although diesel engines are widely used due to their high efficiency and durability, they are one of the primary sources of serious environmental and health-damaging emissions such as NO_x and particulate matter. In the face of increasing energy demand and declining oil reserves, natural gas, in particular, stands out as an important alternative fuel for diesel engines due to its low carbon content, low PM/NO_x emissions, and wide availability. (Wei and Geng 2016). Dual-fuel engines can maintain the efficiency advantages of conventional diesel engines while achieving significant reductions in NO_x and particulate emissions through the combined use of diesel pilot injection and gas fuel. The effects of different gas fuel types on the performance, combustion dynamics, and emission profiles of dual-fuel diesel engines have been observed in conjunction with engine design and operating parameters (Sahoo, Sahoo et al. 2009). In line with increasing environmental requirements, biogas is considered an alternative energy source for internal combustion engines due to its methane-rich composition and renewable nature. However, the physical and chemical properties of biogas, such as its low lower heating value, high CO₂ content, low flame propagation speed, and high auto-ignition temperature, limit its use as a single fuel in compression-ignition engines. Nevertheless, when appropriate purification, compression, and mixing strategies are applied, biogas can support engine performance with low PM emissions, good knock resistance, and improved combustion characteristics. (YILMAZ, YAVUZ et al.) Biodiesel and hydrogen are two important alternative fuels for diesel engines that aim for lower carbon-based emissions due to their chemical properties. Biodiesel improves combustion with its oxygen content, while hydrogen has the potential to increase thermal efficiency with its high flame propagation speed. However, biodiesel's viscosity and oxidative stability issues, along with hydrogen's high ignition

temperature and storage difficulties, limit their direct use, especially in compression-ignition engines. (Şahin and Aktaş).

Diesel engines, which have a wide range of applications due to their high efficiency and durability, pose a significant problem in terms of pollutant emissions such as NO_x and particulate matter. Consequently, increasingly stringent environmental regulations are driving engine designers toward systems that produce lower emissions and alternative fuel solutions. In this context, the dual-fuel diesel engine concept has emerged as an attractive approach because it allows a second gas fuel to be incorporated into the system while retaining the ignition advantages of diesel. In this system, the gas fuel is typically mixed with the intake air and sent to the cylinder; the energy required to initiate combustion is provided by only a small amount of sprayed diesel pilot fuel. Thus, the low carbon content, high hydrogen ratio, and clean combustion properties of the gas fuel can be utilized without changing the basic operating principle of the engine. Significant reductions in emissions such as CO₂, soot, and PM are achieved, especially with the use of methane-based fuels. However, the dual-fuel combustion structure also has some performance limitations, such as low flame propagation speed, delayed ignition, non-homogeneous in-cylinder mixture, and unburned methane emissions, especially at low loads.

On the other hand, various studies have shown that gas fuel addition increases combustion efficiency, reduces NO_x and PM levels, and decreases diesel consumption at medium and high loads. Furthermore, the fact that a large portion of existing diesel engines can be made suitable for dual-fuel operation with only minor modifications strengthens the engineering feasibility of this technology. In addition to natural gas and biogas, research on the use of renewable or synthetic gas fuels such as hydrogen in engines has also increased significantly in recent years. Hydrogen's high flame speed, wide flammability limits, and zero-carbon structure offer the potential to increase efficiency and reduce emissions in dual-fuel engines. Similarly, low-calorific value fuels such as biogas and synthesis gas can contribute to sustainable energy goals in terms of both waste management and carbon neutrality. These approaches position dual-fuel diesel engines as an important interim solution or complementary technology in low-carbon transportation and energy conversion.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study aims to investigate the combustion, performance, and emission behavior of dual-fuel diesel engines using gaseous fuels as a secondary fuel; to evaluate the effects of different gas types (natural gas, biogas, hydrogen, and synthesis gas), mixture ratios, and operating conditions on engine characteristics. The findings aim to contribute to the development of alternative fuel technologies and to the identification of engineering solutions for reducing the environmental impact of diesel engines.

2.1. Natural Gas (NG)

Efforts to reduce harmful emissions in direct-injection diesel engines have increased, and in this context, dual-fuel systems using clean-burning gaseous fuels such as natural gas in addition to diesel fuel have emerged as an important solution. Natural gas's high auto-ignition temperature and low impurity content allow it to be used in existing diesel engines without changing the compression ratio, enabling the almost complete elimination of particulate formation. In the dual-fuel operating principle, the gas fuel mixes with the intake air, and combustion is initiated by the diesel pilot fuel injected towards the end of compression. Experimental studies have shown that increasing the natural gas ratio alters ignition delay, heat release behavior, and combustion duration, but in turn provides significant improvements in

emissions under certain operating conditions. (Papagiannakis and Hountalas 2003). Natural gas is considered one of the most advantageous alternative fuels for internal combustion engines due to its high octane number, clean combustion characteristics, and wide availability, and the dual-fuel operating concept makes it possible to utilize these advantages in diesel engines. In dual-fuel mode, the gas fuel is drawn into the cylinder with the intake air, but since it does not ignite spontaneously due to its high ignition temperature, combustion is initiated by a diesel pilot injection; thus, the contribution of diesel to power generation is limited. Previous research in this field has shown that parameters such as injection timing, pilot fuel quantity, gas-air mixing method, EGR, and intake air heating are decisive for performance and emissions. Although efficiency loss and increases in CO and HC emissions are observed, especially at low loads, significant reductions in NO_x and particulate formation can be achieved under appropriate operating conditions. (Lounici, Loubar et al. 2014).

2.2. Biogas

Biogas is a mixture of methane and non-flammable gases; methane enrichment increases its suitability as a motor fuel. In CI engines, biogas is generally used in dual-fuel mode; the biogas–air mixture is compressed and ignited with pilot diesel. In HCCI mode, the mixture is taken homogeneously and self-ignites at the end of compression. Studies show that biogas reduces NO_x and smoke emissions but decreases brake thermal efficiency and volumetric efficiency while increasing HC and CO emissions. Biogas is particularly suitable for high diesel replacement at high torque. (Feroskhan and Ismail 2017). When examining the performance of a hybrid biogas-diesel dual-fuel engine running on biogas with different CH₄ ratios, the results show that cylinder pressure and cycle work decrease as the CH₄ ratio decreases and engine speed increases. The highest work was achieved with a slightly rich mixture. While rich biogas and 10% pilot injection enabled the engine to produce power equivalent to diesel mode, higher pilot injection was required for biogas with a CH₄ ratio below 70%. When biogas is insufficient, the engine can automatically switch to diesel mode. The concept is a suitable solution for variable biogas conditions. (Van Ga, Hai et al. 2015).

2.3. Hydrogen

Global emission targets have made the use of carbon-free fuels in diesel engines important, and hydrogen has come to the fore in this context. Although hydrogen improves combustion due to its high flame speed and good mixing properties, it cannot ignite on its own and is therefore used in dual-fuel mode with diesel pilot fuel. Studies show that adding hydrogen reduces CO₂, CO, HC, and particulate formation; however, due to the increase in combustion temperature, it raises NO_x values in most cases. In terms of performance, hydrogen increases efficiency, especially at medium to high loads, but its low density can negatively affect filling efficiency by reducing the amount of air. Methods such as EGR, water injection, and reducing the compression ratio are commonly recommended for NO_x control (Rueda-Vázquez, Serrano et al. 2024). The hydrogen-diesel dual fuel mode stands out as a current approach to alternative fuel use in diesel engines. For this method to be applied efficiently, the fuel system must operate under ECU control, and injection settings must be correctly determined. When evaluating the effects of different hydrogen energy ratios and injection timings on engine performance, emissions, noise, and vibration, experiments conducted at constant speed and load revealed significant improvements in NO_x and energy consumption, particularly at a 14% hydrogen energy ratio and 30°CA aTDC timing. As a result, important findings were obtained regarding the determination of the optimum hydrogen ratio and injection timing in HDDF engines (Gültekin 2024).

2.4. Synthesis Gas

Synthesis gas is a variable-composition fuel obtained by gasifying biomass and has gained

importance among alternative and cleaner energy options. Variability in composition is a key parameter that must be controlled, as it significantly affects engine performance and emission behavior. Synthesis gas can be used in dual-fuel mode in CI engines, and this mode can reduce emissions and NO_x values while increasing CO emissions. The literature shows that different types of gasifiers have different effects on engine combustion in typical synthesis gas compositions. The effects of pilot diesel quantity and equivalence ratio on performance and emissions were experimentally investigated using three representative synthesis gas compositions, and the operating limits of dual-fuel CI engines were defined by determining the contribution of synthesis gas components to combustion processes (De Castro, Brequigny et al. 2022). Synthesis gas is an energy source obtained from gasified biomass and has a variable composition. To more accurately examine the effect of this variability on engine performance, three controlled artificial syngas compositions representing real gasifier conditions were used. The results obtained were compared with diesel operation at 2000 rpm, and power, consumption, and efficiency criteria were evaluated. The tests showed that syngas use provided lower brake power and brake thermal efficiency compared to diesel mode. Furthermore, it was determined that differences in the synthesis gas composition significantly altered the engine's performance response (Mahgoub, Sulaiman et al. 2013).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Use of natural gas as a secondary fuel in compression-ignition engines with dual-fuel injection

Yasin Karagöz and Tarkan Sandalcı (Karagöz, Sandalcı et al. 2016) adapted a single-cylinder diesel engine for dual-fuel operation using a common rail diesel injection system and a CNG injector added to the intake manifold. Diesel and natural gas flows were measured with precision flow meters, and cylinder pressure, temperatures, and emissions were recorded with advanced sensors. The entire system was controlled with a specially designed hybrid ECU and LabVIEW-based data acquisition software. The experiments were conducted on a 40 kW eddy current dynamometer, and the performance and emission behavior of the engine in different fuel modes were compared. Overall, the setup enabled a detailed analysis of the combustion and performance characteristics of the dual-fuel CI engine running with natural gas support.

Seungchul Woo, Juho Lee, Kihyung Lee (Woo, Lee et al. 2021) investigated the effect of air-fuel ratio on performance and emissions in a 1.0 L three-cylinder LPG-injected engine. The engine was equipped with an adjustable control unit instead of a standard ECU and operated at different AFR values. LPG consumption was measured in real time using a Coriolis flowmeter placed in the supply and return lines. The experiments were conducted at engine speeds of 1500–3000 rpm and loads of 2–6 kg·m, and the leanest mixture limit at which the engine could operate stably was determined. The results showed that the air-fuel ratio has a significant effect on fuel consumption, combustion characteristics, emissions, and engine efficiency; with proper AFR adjustment, performance improvement and lower emissions can be achieved in LPG engines.

ViniciusB Pedrozo and Xinyan Wang (Pedrozo, Wang et al. 2022) set up a special experimental setup to investigate dual-fuel combustion behavior on a single-cylinder compression ignition engine. The experimental system was equipped with an eddy current dynamometer to absorb the power produced by the engine. Fresh air supplied to the engine was provided via an external compressor operating with pressure feedback control; the intake manifold pressure was precisely adjusted using a butterfly valve placed before the surge tank. The mass flow rate of the intake air was measured using a thermal flow meter, and its temperature was controlled using a water-cooled heat exchanger. A second surge tank was used in the exhaust line to reduce

pressure fluctuations, and the desired back pressure was provided by an electronically controlled backpressure valve. The heavy-duty engine used in the study features a four-valve cylinder head that creates a swirl effect, a stepped piston bowl geometry, and a high-strength combustion chamber structure. The lubrication and cooling circuits were driven by independent electric motors, and the engine oil and cooling water temperatures were kept constant at 85°C throughout the experiment. In addition, the oil pressure was maintained at 450 kPa to ensure the repeatability of the measurements. Using these methods, the pressure, flow, and temperature parameters of the engine in dual-fuel mode were controlled and varied, making the combustion process reliably observable.

3.2. Use of biogas as a secondary fuel in compression ignition engines with dual fuel

In his study (Ambarita, 2017), Ambarita found that the use of biogas as a secondary fuel in diesel engines provided a slight increase in engine power because it carried additional energy to the combustion chamber. Although thermal efficiency improved at low biogas flow rates, increasing the flow rate lowered the combustion temperature, leading to a decrease in efficiency. Dual fuel use increased specific fuel consumption; while raising unburned emissions such as CO and HC, it significantly reduced smoke levels. As the biogas ratio and methane content increased, diesel consumption decreased significantly, but combustion quality was negatively affected at very high biogas ratios. These findings indicate that the amount of biogas must be carefully selected in dual-fuel operation. In the study by İlker Turgut YILMAZ, Mustafa YAVUZ, Metin GÜMÜŞ (Yılmaz, Yavuz et al. 2020), a mixing chamber was added between the air filter and the turbocharger to make the diesel engine suitable for dual-fuel operation with biogas, and the compression ratio of the engine was reduced by using an additional gasket. The biogas used in the experiments contained 60% CH₄ and 40% CO₂, and the gas flow rates were monitored using mechanical valve flow meters and mass flow meters. Diesel consumption was determined using a high-precision fuel gauge and a stopwatch. While the engine was kept constant at 1750 rpm, the load was varied between 40–80 Nm; dual fuel conditions were created by replacing 20–50% of the diesel quantity determined with single fuel with biogas. The experiments were conducted in triplicate, with exhaust emissions measured using a Bosch BEA 460 device and engine parameters monitored via the electronic control unit.

In their work, Yoon and Lee (Yoon and Lee 2011) used a four-cylinder, turbocharged, prechamber compression ignition engine test rig. The basic characteristics of the engine are: 91.1 mm cylinder bore, 95.0 mm stroke, 2476 cm³ displacement, and a compression ratio of 19:1. The maximum power was recorded at 15.21 kW at 4000 rpm, and the maximum torque was recorded at 63.67 Nm at 2000 rpm. In the experiments, the engine was run at a constant speed of 2000 rpm, and the injection start was set to 12° BTDC. To examine the combustion characteristics, the engine was tested in both single fuel (diesel and biodiesel) and dual fuel modes. Intra-cylinder pressure changes and the rate of heat release (ROHR) were recorded as a function of load increase and compared between fuel types. The results revealed that diesel and biodiesel exhibit similar combustion tendencies, but as load increases, pressure and heat release rates rise significantly.

3.3. The use of hydrogen as a secondary fuel in compression-ignition engines

Seyyed Hassan Hosseini and Athanasios Tsolakis found in their work (Hosseini, Tsolakis et al. 2023) that the use of hydrogen as a secondary fuel in diesel engines significantly reduces carbon-containing emissions (CO, HC, soot) but tends to increase NO_x formation because it raises the combustion temperature. The pilot diesel/biodiesel amount directly affects ignition stability in the dual-fuel mode with hydrogen and is decisive in controlling the combustion process. Studies with gaseous fuels and synthesis gas have shown that hydrogen can improve mixture homogeneity and increase efficiency but can also cause performance fluctuations

depending on the engine load. Inert gas dilution, HHO use, and fuel mixture optimization stand out as effective solutions for reducing NO_x tendencies. Overall, it has been concluded that hydrogen use makes the engine run cleaner but requires additional optimization for NO_x control and combustion stability.

Frengki Mohamad Felayatia, Hadi Prasutiyon, and colleagues (Felayati, Prasutiyon et al. 2024) investigated the effect of oxyhydrogen injection on diesel engine performance and emissions at different injector diameters and engine speeds. At low engine speeds, oxyhydrogen limited air intake, resulting in poor mixture homogeneity, delayed ignition, and reduced engine torque. At high speeds, however, improved mixture and faster combustion led to increased torque. Medium injector diameters were found to yield more balanced results in terms of both fuel consumption and emissions. The addition of oxyhydrogen generally reduced specific fuel consumption, increased thermal efficiency, and reduced CO emissions; however, CO₂ increased under certain conditions. In general, oxyhydrogen has the potential to improve the combustion quality and efficiency of diesel engines when the appropriate injector size and engine operating conditions are provided.

In his study, Nurullah Gültekin (Gültekin 2024) investigated the effect of hydrogen ratio and injection timing on performance and emissions in a hydrogen-diesel dual-fuel CI engine. It was observed that when the hydrogen ratio was increased up to 14%, the engine's thermal efficiency increased, energy consumption decreased, and combustion pressure increased. At higher hydrogen ratios, combustion efficiency decreased due to restricted air intake. The use of hydrogen reduced CO, HC, and soot emissions, but led to an increase in NO emissions, engine noise, and vibration. The decrease in volumetric efficiency was partially improved by delaying hydrogen injection. Consequently, determining the appropriate hydrogen ratio and timing provides advantages in terms of system performance and carbon-based emissions, but requires further improvement in terms of NO and NVH.

3.4. Use of synthesis gas as a secondary fuel in compression-ignition engines with dual-fuel injection

Bahaaddein K.M. Mahgoub, S.A. Sulaiman, and Z.A. Abdul Karim (Mahgoub, Sulaiman et al. 2015) compared the performance of synthesis gas with diesel fuel at different engine speeds. As engine speed increased, the diesel replacement ratio decreased due to the increase in diesel flow rate corresponding to a constant synthesis gas flow rate. It was determined that the exhaust temperature tended to decrease under all test conditions as the amount of synthesis gas increased. It was stated that the change in exhaust temperature was directly related to the combustible gas ratios and combustion characteristics of the synthesis gas. In general, the change in exhaust temperature became more pronounced as engine speed increased due to more fuel entering the cylinder.

In their study (De Castro, Brequigny et al. 2022), De Castro and Brequigny kept the injection duration constant and increased the amount of syngas added to the mixture to observe the effect of the syngas/air mixture ratio on engine operating behavior. The premix equivalence ratio was tested at different levels, but it was observed that high ratios led to unstable combustion in some syngas types. The injection timing was optimized to achieve maximum IMEP. The analyses showed that the syngas composition has significant effects on engine performance and emissions. It was concluded that high thermal efficiencies could be achieved without making major structural changes to the engine. In their work, Yaliwal and Banapurmath (Yaliwal and Banapurmath 2021) tested the effects of gas and hydrogen obtained from biodiesel-treated biomass on dual-fuel operation in a diesel engine. The hydrogen flow rate was kept constant, and the experiments were conducted at different engine loads. The results revealed how the use of hydrogen-blended and unblended fuels altered combustion and emission behavior. The

performance differences of the produced gas compared to the diesel dual-fuel mode were evaluated. Thus, the effects of fuel compositions on engine performance were systematically compared.

Hongsheng Guo, W. Stuart Neill, Brian Liko (Guo, Neill et al. 2016) found that increasing the synthesis gas ratio prolonged ignition delay due to the high ignition temperature of H₂ and CO and slightly increased intake pressure. Cylinder peak pressure increased slightly, independent of engine load, but brake thermal efficiency decreased significantly, especially at low loads. The main reason for this efficiency loss is the incomplete combustion of CO and H₂ at low temperatures. In emission analyses, soot formation changed very little at low syngas ratios, while soot emissions decreased at high ratios. NO_x emissions decreased continuously with the syngas ratio, while CO emissions increased due to incomplete combustion. Overall, the results show that syngas use lowers engine temperatures, affects efficiency, and makes emission behavior sensitive to fuel composition.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the effects of natural gas, biogas, hydrogen, and synthesis gas used as secondary fuels in diesel engines in dual-fuel mode were evaluated in line with the literature. The investigations showed that these four gaseous fuels affect engine performance and emissions in different ways, each carrying advantages and limitations under specific conditions.

✓ Natural gas stands out as one of the most preferred gas fuels in diesel engines due to its high octane number and clean combustion properties. Its significant advantages include requiring no major changes to existing engine designs and reducing NO_x and particulate emissions. However, the slow combustion of natural gas at low loads can lead to efficiency losses. At medium and high loads, however, gas addition provides a more stable combustion process and reduces diesel consumption.

✓ Biogas is an environmentally valuable fuel due to its renewable nature and methane content. When used in dual-fuel mode, it significantly reduces smoke emissions. However, the high CO₂ content in biogas lowers the combustion temperature, so a decrease in thermal efficiency may be observed with excessive biogas use. It has been determined that engine performance improves as the methane content increases, but combustion quality deteriorates at very high biogas flow rates. Therefore, it is important to maintain the biogas ratio at an optimal level.

✓ Hydrogen is a carbon-free fuel that can accelerate combustion due to its high flame speed and wide flammability range. Hydrogen addition significantly reduces carbon-based emissions such as CO, HC, and smoke. It also increases engine efficiency at medium and high loads. On the other hand, NO_x emissions may increase because hydrogen combustion raises the temperature. Hydrogen's reduction of the amount of air entering the cylinder can also lead to efficiency losses at low loads. Therefore, injection timing and hydrogen ratio must be carefully adjusted.

✓ Synthesis gas is a fuel with a variable composition, and engine behavior is directly dependent on the ratios of H₂, CO, and inert gases it contains. It is generally not suitable for use alone; however, when used with diesel pilot fuel, it can reduce soot and NO_x emissions. Incomplete combustion of synthesis gas at low temperatures can cause efficiency losses at low loads. More balanced combustion can be achieved with the appropriate amount of pilot diesel and the correct air-fuel ratio.

✓ Overall, natural gas offers the most balanced performance-emission relationship, while biogas provides advantages in terms of sustainability. Hydrogen has the highest efficiency and

lowest carbon combustion potential, while synthesis gas is particularly noteworthy for emission reduction due to its low-temperature combustion. For all these fuel types, correctly determining the engine load, fuel ratio, injection timing, and mixture conditions enables both performance maintenance and environmental impact reduction in dual-fuel diesel engines.

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